

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

EOM4SOIL

Deliverable WP6 – T1.

Multicriteria evaluation system for EOMs use

Due date of deliverable: MX
Actual submission date: 15.11.2024

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Programme title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Programme website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Project title: EOM4SOIL

Project website:

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	WP6 – T1.
DELIVERABLE TITLE:	Multicriteria evaluation system for EOMs use
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Report
WORK PACKAGE N:	WP6
WORK PACKAGE TITLE:	Multicriteria evaluation system for EOMs use
DELIVERABLE LEADER:	INRAE
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DOI:	
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DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	CO/PU

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

AMG	Automated model generation
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
awc	Available water capacity
C	Carbon
Cd	Cadmium
Cr	Chromium
Cu	Copper
d	Soil density
EOM	External organic matter
EU	European union
GHG	Greenhouse gas
Hg	Mercury
K	Potassium
LTE	Long term field experiment
N	Nitrogen
N₂O	Nitrous oxide
NH₃	Ammonia
NH₄-N	Ammonium nitrogen
Ni	Nickel
NO₃	Nitrate
P	Phosphorus
Pb	Lead
SOC	Soil organic carbon
SOM	Soil organic matter
STICS	Simulateur multidisciplinaire pour les cultures standard
TE	Trace elements
WP	Work package
Year 1	First year of application
Year 30	30 years of application
Zn	Zinc

1. INTRODUCTION

Minimizing the ecological footprint of food production is a crucial strategy for promoting sustainability in agriculture, and one effective approach is recycling external organic materials (EOM) into a valuable resource. The application of EOM in agricultural soils is essential for enhancing crop yield (Caron et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2024), maintaining soil fertility (Maffia et al., 2024; Paradelo et al., 2024), and mitigating climate change impacts (Hall et al., 2022). This approach, which aligns the interactions among agriculture, the environment, and waste management, has led to continuous advancements in research on the EOM recycling in agricultural soil systems. Several studies have thoroughly investigated the significance of EOM in promoting sustainable agricultural practices across various aspects: soil health, crop productivity, environmental considerations, and integration into the circular economy (Brichi et al., 2023). Prominent research themes include enhancing carbon (C) sequestration in soils (Bai et al., 2023), optimizing nitrogen (N) management to improve efficiency (Chen et al., 2022), and increasing the availability of key soil nutrients, such as phosphorus (P) (Kataria et al., 2024). Assessing the risks related to soil contamination from repeated EOM applications has also become a major focus (Singh Gautam et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024). However, most of these evaluations were conducted in controlled research settings with specific experiments.

The effects of EOM application to agricultural soils are influenced by factors such as EOM type (origin and treatment), cropping systems, soil characteristics and climate. These factors vary widely across different regions and countries. For instance, Ogle et al., (2005) demonstrated that organic amendments enhance C storage more effectively in moist tropical climates than in temperate regions. Wang et al. (2024) added that temperature and precipitation are correlated with soil organic carbon (SOC) content. Additionally, Bai et al. (2023) highlighted that organic amendments have a stronger long-term impact on SOC storage in arid, alkaline soils compared to humid, acidic soils. The effects of EOM are also strongly influenced by the application rate and frequency (Zhou et al., 2022). Treatments such as anaerobic digestion to produce digestate or composting of manure can significantly influence the effects of applying these EOM on N availability, N losses, and greenhouse gas (GHG) emission compared to raw manure (Crolla et al., 2013; Khadim et al., 2024). Moreover, the use of EOM by farmers also depends on various drivers (e.g., perceived effects on soil quality, influence of social referent) and barriers (financial, EOM availability, perceived EOM pollution) (Hijbeek et al., 2019). Overall, these findings underscore the importance of considering these factors when evaluating the effects of EOM in agricultural systems. Long term field experiment (LTE) aimed at studying the EOM effects are often constrained by their substantial economic burdens, which limit their capacity to capture the full variability of influencing factors, such as cropping systems, EOM types, soil properties, and climate. As a result, LTE designs frequently simplify cropping systems (e.g., through short rotations or removal of crop residues) and apply EOM at higher rates and frequencies than typically observed in agricultural practice, facilitating a more rapid detection of EOM effects. However, these methodological adjustments may limit the applicability of LTE findings to standard agricultural systems and diverse environmental contexts. This gap emphasizes the urgent need for practical research that closely aligns with real-world farming

scenarios, addressing the economic and environmental challenges agricultural producers face following EOM application.

To address the trade-offs and maximize the benefit of the EOM application, it is essential to align research on EOM effects with supportive policy and promote adaptive changes in farmers' practices. Levavasseur and Houot (2022) introduced the PROLEG tool, an integrated approach for multi-criteria evaluation of EOM application effects. This tool can explicitly consider different EOM, soil types, cropping system and climates. By incorporating these parameters, the PROLEG tool can significantly aid in evaluating various EOM application scenarios, offering insights into maximizing agronomic and environmental benefits while minimizing losses and negative impacts, such as GHG emissions and soil contamination. Currently, the tool has been used only in a specific region. However, expanding the use of the tool across a broader range of case studies with varied pedoclimatic and cropping system conditions could provide valuable data on EOM effects, to optimize its applications in diverse farming systems for both short- and long-term effects.

In the context of increasing environmental challenges and the need for sustainable agricultural practices, this study aims to comprehensively assess the multiple effects of EOM recycling across various regional conditions in Europe, emphasizing the current utilization of EOM. This assessment will develop practical guidelines for optimizing EOM application in diverse European agricultural systems. To achieve these objectives, the research will define existing cropping systems, both with and without EOM, through representative case studies that consider different soils, climates, and cropping practices across contrasted regional conditions in Europe. Subsequently, the agronomic and environmental performance of these cropping systems will be simulated. Insights derived from these simulations will facilitate the formulation of actionable strategies to enhance EOM management, while also contributing to broader efforts aimed at promoting sustainable farming practices and mitigating climate change impacts across various European regions.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. PROLEG, an integrated multicriteria evaluation tools

The PROLEG tool is used to evaluate the EOM application in agricultural fields. This tool integrates various models and functions to predict the agronomic and environmental performance of cropping systems, particularly those that recycle organic wastes. The tool, developed in the R programming language, uses the AMG model (Clivot et al., 2019) to predict both the soil organic matter (SOM) and SOC content and stocks. It integrates the Alfam model (Hafner et al., 2019) to simulate ammonia (NH₃) volatilization under EOM applications. The soil-crop model STICS (Simulateur multidisciplinaire pour les cultures standard) (Brisson et al., 2009) is used to predict N (except NH₃) and water fluxes through the soil. Additionally, it incorporates some pedotransfer functions to estimate the evolution of different soil properties along SOC. The GHG balance is also computed in the tool. An important feature of the tool is its ability to calculate the required amount of mineral N fertilizer to fulfill crop N requirements, considering the nutrients provided by the soil, both in the short term and cumulatively over repeated EOM applications in long term. For P and K, a simplified approach computes the P

and K balance based on P and K inputs from EOM applications and crop exports. In case of a negative balance, the tool adjusts the amount of minerals P and K applied. The simulation generated by this tool is based on existing database parameter tables for EOM characteristics, machinery, and crops and on the description of the cropping system, soil characteristics and climate. For a full description of the PROLEG tool, see Levavasseur et al., (2023).

2.2. Data collection and analysis

2.2.1. Data collection

Data on how farmers currently use EOM was collected in collaboration with experts from various European institutes to capture diverse pedo-climatic and cropping system conditions. Partners were approached for data collection. However, challenges like time constraints and varying expertise made it difficult to gather data from all regions. The study focused on representative datasets from farmers actively using EOM. The selected EOM types included those commonly used or emerging, based on the cropping systems of each region. The study covered four contrasted regions in France, along with areas in Wallonia (Belgium), the Netherlands, Lithuania, and Turkey, providing a broad representation of agricultural practices across Europe (Figure 1). The climates utilized in this study were specified for each study area. Data were collected from the Gridded Agro-Meteorological Data in Europe (<https://agri4cast.jrc.ec.europa.eu/DataPortal/Index.aspx>). Different EOM scenarios were grouped based on their pedoclimatic and cropping system conditions. Each group also includes a reference scenario that uses only mineral fertilizers as a control, allowing for direct comparisons between the effects of EOM and mineral treatments

Figure 1 : Map of selected countries for data collection (source: <https://www.mapchart.net/europe.html>)

2.2.2. Simulation and data analysis

The annual nutrient inputs (N, P, K) provided by the different types of EOM in the cropping systems were calculated based on the mean characteristics of the EOM incorporated into the model (i.e., the potential specific EOM characteristics in a given area were not considered, due to limited data availability). Simulations were conducted using the PROLEG tool to evaluate performance over a five-year climatic period (2017-2021). The simulations were conducted for two different periods: the first year of EOM application (Year 1) and after 30 years of continuous EOM use (Year 30). These periods were selected to assess both the short-term and long-term impacts of EOM on cropping systems. In all scenario simulations, N, P, and K applications were adjusted by the tool.

The parameters assessed included N supply, P and K balances, and N losses through NO₃ leaching, NH₃ volatilization, and nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions. Additional soil quality indicators, such as soil C storage, available water capacity (awc), soil density (d_{soil}), and microbial biomass (m_{microbial biomass}) were evaluated. The greenhouse gas balance was computed, considering, soil C storage, soil N₂O emissions (direct and indirect), GHG emissions related to mineral fertilizer and EOM productions and to fuel consumption. The increase in soil trace metal content was computed for cadmium (Cd), copper (Cu), nickel (Ni), lead (Pb), zinc (Zn), mercury (Hg), and chromium (Cr), considering both EOM and mineral P fertilizer input. The target variables were calculated as the difference between the outcomes with EOM application and those with mineral-only treatments within each group of scenarios, except for the P and K balances, which were recorded as absolute values for each scenario. Table 1 presents the equations used to compute these differential effects.

Table 1 : Calculation of target variable values: the differences between outcomes under EOM application and mineral fertilizer across scenario groups

	Equation for the target variables
Nutrient availability	
N supply	$\Delta N_{supply}(OW) = N_{supply}(OW) - N_{supply}(mineral)$
P balance	$P_{balance}(OW)$
K balance	$K_{balance}(OW)$
Nitrogen losses	
Ammonium lixiviation	$\Delta NH_{4leached}(OW) = N_{leached}(OW) - N_{leached}(mineral)$
N ammonia volatilization	$\Delta NH_{3volatilized}(OW) = N_{volatilized}(OW) - N_{volatilized}(mineral)$
Nitrous oxide emissions	$\Delta N_2O_{emission}(OW) = N_2O_{emission}(OW) - N_2O_{emission}(mineral)$
Soil quality indicators	
Carbon storage	$\Delta C_{storage}(OW) = C_{storage}(OW) - C_{storage}(mineral)$
Available water capacity	$\Delta awc(OW) = awc(OW) - awc(mineral)$
Soil density	$\Delta d_{soil}(OW) = d_{soil}(OW) - d_{soil}(OW)$
Microbial biomass	$\Delta m_{microbial\ biomass}(OW) = m_{microbial\ biomass}(OW) - m_{microbial\ biomass}(mineral)$
Environmental impact indicator	
Elements of trace metals	$\Delta ETM_{soil}(OW) = ETM_{soil}(OW) - ETM_{soil}(mineral)$
Greenhouse gas emissions	$\Delta GHG_{emission}(OW) = GHG_{emission}(OW) - GHG_{emission}(mineral)$

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied to evaluate the effects of the simulation period (Year 1 and Year 30) on N supply, N losses, C storage, and GHG emissions. The ANOVA was conducted using R software (version 4.4.1) with a significance threshold set at P<0.05. The results of the simulations, using all target variables in Table 1, were visualized using boxplots

for the simulated years, combining data from all regions, soil types, and cropping systems to highlight the variability of EOM effects across our case studies. Details of the results per case study are in supplementary information.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Varied scenarios of cropping systems using external organic matter

The data collected in table 2 revealed a large diversity of pedoclimatic conditions, cropping systems across various European countries. Concurrently, sources of EOM applications in each region are detailed in Figure A1. In the Versailles plain, characterized by an oceanic climate, cereal-based cropping systems are prominent, with EOM derived from urban waste applied on luvisol soils (Figure A1). This urban-derived EOM represents an opportunity for EOM recycling within an urban-adjacent agricultural system, enhancing nutrient circulation between urban and agricultural areas. In contrast, the region of Brittany, where livestock farming is more intensive, relies heavily on livestock-derived EOM (Figure A1), which is applied to cambisol soils of varying depths within a crop rotation system focused on cereals and forage (Table 2). This reliance on livestock-sourced EOM underlines the importance of animal husbandry in the region's agricultural framework, providing a renewable source of organic amendments. The Alsace region, with its semi-continental climate, predominantly supports cereals production on shallow calcareous rendzic leptosols and deeper calcisols (Table 2) where both EOM from livestock and urban waste are applied (Figure A1). In southwestern France, specifically in the Gers and Lauragais regions, besides cereal systems, these areas incorporate industrial crop (sunflower) on fluvisol and cambisol soils (Table 2), and the sources of EOM include livestock farming, urban waste, and digestate from energy crop (Figure A1). This diversification not only supports agricultural productivity but also facilitates energy crop rotations, thereby integrating bioenergy production with sustainable nutrient recycling.

Other European countries exhibit also diverse approaches to EOM integration based on their distinct pedoclimatic conditions and agricultural priorities. In Belgium's Wallonia region, the temperate oceanic climates support diversified or mixed cropping systems, such as cereals grown cultivated alongside industrial or forage crops on luvisols soil (Table 2). The EOM sources are derived from livestock farming and industry by-products, creating a synergy between agricultural and industrial sectors (Table A1). In Turkey, under a mediterranean climate, agricultural is dominated by cereal-based systems that utilize EOM from livestock farming applied to haplic luvisol soils (Table 2 and Table A1). Lithuania's humid continental climate supports a different agricultural model, where cereals and forage crops are cultivated on luvisol soils, relying predominantly on EOM from livestock (Table 2 and Table A1). Finally, in the Netherlands, a diversified industrial cropping system thrives on histosols within an oceanic climate. This system benefits from EOM sourced from both livestock and urban waste (Table 2 and Table A1).

Table 2 : Summary of the different case studies considered in our study across different regions in France, Belgium, Turkey, Lithuania, and the Netherlands

Region	Cropping systems	Soils types	Group ^(a)
France			
Versailles plain <i>Oceanic climate</i>	Rapeseed - winter wheat – mustard ^(b) - grain maize - winter wheat - winter barley	Haplic luvisol	A
	Rapeseed - winter wheat - winter wheat - winter barley	Luvisol	B
Brittany <i>Oceanic climate</i>	Winter wheat - mustard ^(b) - silage maize	Cambisol (moderately deep soil)	C
		Cambisol (deep soil)	D
	Winter wheat - rye or barley ^(c) - silage maize	Cambisol (moderately deep soil)	E
		Cambisol (deep soil)	F
Alsace <i>Semi-continental climate</i>	Grain maize - grain maize - grain maize - winter wheat - mustard ^(b) - soyabean	Rendzic leptosols (calcaric shallow soil)	G
		Calcisol (deep soil)	H
Gers <i>Oceanic climate</i>	Grain maize - grain maize - grain maize	Fluvisol (deep soil)	I
Lauragais <i>Oceanic climate</i>	Durum wheat - sunflower	Cambisol (calcaric soil)	J
	Durum wheat - sunflower - rye or barley ^(c)	Cambisol (calcaric soil)	K
Belgium			
Wallonia Brugelette <i>Temperate oceanic climate</i>	Mixture of legumes ^(b) - sugar beet - winter wheat - mixture of legumes ^(b) - consumption potatoes - winter wheat	Haplic luvisol	L
Wallonia Awans <i>Temperate oceanic climate</i>	Winter wheat – rapeseed - crucifers ^(b) - consumption potatoes - winter wheat- mixture of legumes ^(b) - peas for canning- mixture of legumes ^(b) - sugar beet	Haplic luvisol	M
Wallonia Huy (Solières) <i>Temperate oceanic climate</i>	Mixture of legumes ^(b) - sugar beet - winter wheat - rapeseed- mixture of legumes ^(b) -silage maize - winter wheat	Haplic luvisol	N
Turkey			
Adana <i>Mediterranean climate</i>	Winter wheat – sunflower	Haplic luvisol	n.s
	Winter wheat – grain maize	Haplic luvisol	n.s
Lithuanic			
Anykščiai - Eastern <i>Humid continental climate</i>	Winter wheat – spring barley - consumption potatoes - spring rapeseed	Haplic Luvisol	n.s
Netherland			
<i>Oceanic climate</i>	Starch potatoes - spring barley - grass cover crop ^(b) - starch potatoes - sugar beet	Histosol	n.s

^(a) Group refers to the scenario group within each region based on variations in cropping systems and soil types used in the simulation.

^(b) Nitrogen catch crop

^(c) Energy cover crop

n.s. not simulated

3.2. Nutrient contributions and soil balances: N supply, P and K balances

The diverse scenarios in this study highlight the significant variability in nutrient applications practices across European regions, influenced by both the EOM type, rate, and frequency of application (Table A1). These regional differences reflect distinct agricultural traditions, resource availability, and soil needs, highlighting how EOM management is tailored to specific cropping systems. The EOM application rates in this study ranged widely, from 9 to 94.5 tons of fresh weight per hectare, with application frequencies varying from 1 to 5 years depending on the region (Table A1). The average annual N inputs range from 18 to 139 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ (Figure 2). This variability is particularly significant given the diversity of EOM types used in agricultural practices, each providing distinct contributions of organic and mineral forms of N. As illustrated in Figure 2, different types of EOM supply varying proportions of organic-N and mineral-N, which has important implications for N management. Notably, EOMs generally supply higher levels of organic-N compared to mineral-N.

In this study, several scenarios with different types of EOMs — including green waste compost, horse manure, cattle manure, green waste and sludge compost, cattle manure compost — each

contributed over $100 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ of organic-N (Figure 2). These high levels of organic-N promote a slow release of N in the first year of application (Chen et al., 2024; Sarker et al., 2023). By contrast, scenarios with EOM types such as biowaste digestate, pig slurry, pig slurry digestate, cattle manure and slurry digestate, provided not only high doses of organic-N but also substantial levels of mineral-N, particularly valuable in regions such as Brittany and Alsace (Figure A1). These EOM types thus offer a dual benefit: they provide readily available N for crops while simultaneously promoting the slow release of N in the long term (Moinard et al., 2024; Wysocka-Czubaszek, 2019). This characteristic enhances both immediate crop growth and long-term soil fertility, reducing the reliance on synthetic fertilizers and supporting more sustainable nutrient management practices. In contrast, scenarios with limed urban sludge, manures, and composts generally (EOM with lower mineral-N content), resulted in slower N release in the short term. The scenarios applications of cattle slurry, biowaste digestate, pig slurry digestate, and energy crop digestate also supplied notable amounts of mineral-N, exceeding $50 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ to the fields (Figure 2).

Given the variability in N quantities provided by different types of EOM, along with differences in their mineral-N and organic-N content, statistical analysis revealed that the simulation period played a significant role in influencing ΔN_{supply} variation, as illustrated in Figure 3. In the first year of application, the ΔN_{supply} average was $27.35 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ (Figure 3). The results indicated that the highest values of ΔN_{supply} , ranging from 40 to $99.77 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$, were observed with types of EOM known for their high mineral-N content, which provides an immediate source of available N in the soil. Notably, scenarios with EOM types such as pig slurry, pig slurry digestate, cattle manure, and slurry digestate delivered the most substantial mineral-N supply, supporting rapid nutrient uptake by crops and enhancing short-term productivity. These were closely followed by scenarios with biowaste digestate and energy crop digestate, which, although slightly lower, still contributed above-average ΔN_{supply} values in first year of application (Figure 3). In contrast, lower ΔN_{supply} values were observed in scenarios involving EOM types such as cattle manure—whether applied alone or in combination with compost or sugar scum, as well as with cattle slurry, limed urban sludge, green waste compost, and green waste and sludge composts in the first year of application (Figure 3). The lower mineral-N content of these EOMs contributes to a slower nutrient release for manure and compost, making them less effective for immediate N availability for short-term N supply (Gutser et al., 2005). Over 30 years of EOM application, the ΔN_{supply} average increased by nearly 50% compared to year 1, reaching $53.88 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ (Figure 3). This increase reflects both the cumulative effects of EOM applications, which generally contribute higher levels of organic-N than mineral-N. For instance, the increases in ΔN_{supply} were observed, following repeated EOM application in scenario involving horse manure, green waste compost, cattle manure, green waste and sludge compost application, which allowed for a reduction in use N mineral fertilizers after 30 years of EOM application. Applying cattle slurry, biowaste digestate, and energy crop digestate also resulted in higher ΔN_{supply} than the ΔN_{supply} average values observed (Figure 3). Notably, the scenario with pig slurry and pig slurry digestate, along with cattle manure and slurry digestate consistently exhibited the highest ΔN_{supply} , ranging from 74.96 to $101.62 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$, after 30 years of EOM applications (Figure 3). These EOM

continue to apply both organic-N and mineral-N with each application, sustaining high N availability over the long term. Additionally, applying EOMs contributed to higher organic-N inputs, which, in turn, strongly increased ΔN_{supply} over the long term (Gutser et al., 2005). However, this could lead to an excess of N supply in the soil over the long term, which may cause nutrient imbalances or increase the risk of N losses.

As shown in Figure 2, the evaluation of P and K dynamics in cropping systems using various types of EOM revealed significant differences in nutrient inputs, with P inputs ranging from 8.2 to 68 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ and K inputs from 1.88 to 153.2 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ year⁻¹. Overall, across all case study groups, EOM application led to increased P and K balance compared to the mineral treatments (Figures A4 and A5). This suggests that nutrient inputs from EOM can significantly alter the nutrient balance in response to crop needs. Furthermore, these inputs may reduce the dependency on mineral P and K fertilizers in cropping systems (de Sousa and Moreira, 2024). Such an approach could facilitate a significant reduction in P and K mineral fertilization requirements, without posing a risk of P and K surpluses (Schut and Reymann, 2023). Additionally, significant differences were observed based on the type of EOM applied, resulting in distinct effects on the soil's P and K balances (P_{balance} and K_{balance}).

Annual P application rates exceeding 40 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ were associated in scenario with pig slurry, pig slurry digestate, cattle manure, cattle slurry, cattle manure and slurry digestate, and green waste and sludge compost. This resulted in predominantly positive P_{balance} values, indicating a P surplus, particularly in scenarios with cattle manure and slurry digestate and pig slurry applications in Brittany, ranging from 3.71 to 13.66 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ (Figure A4), under the applications of 53.65 to 68 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ year⁻¹. The surplus highlights these EOM types as effective sources of P, potentially supplying amounts that not only meet crop demand but could also pose a risk of environmental runoff if not carefully managed (de Sousa and Moreira, 2024; Marchezan et al., 2023; Rosemarin et al., 2021). Slightly simulated negative P_{balance} values ($P_{\text{balance}} > -2$ kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ year⁻¹) were observed by applying pig slurry digestate and cattle manure and slurry digestate, still in Brittany, across different crop rotation systems and soil types. This confirms the importance of cropping systems in influencing the effects of EOM applications. They also suggested a need for better adjustment of application rates, taking into account the crop requirements. In contrast, fields receiving green waste compost, biowaste digestate, energy crop digestate, lime urban sludge, horse manure, cattle slurry, cattle manure, and cattle manure compost display significantly lower P_{balance} values compared to the average ($P_{\text{balance}} < -23$ kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ year⁻¹), with deficits reaching up to -68.28 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ year⁻¹. These deficits were observed following low P input levels, ranging from 8 to 44 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ across cropping systems, suggesting a misalignment between P input rates and crop needs. These results highlight the importance of selecting EOM sources that can adequately meet crop P requirements when relying solely on EOM in the field or complementing with mineral P fertilizer. Ensuring P supply with crop needs is essential to prevent P deficiencies, improve nutrient use efficiency, and minimize environmental risks associated with P loss (Hu et al., 2021).

Figure 2 : Mean yearly Nitrogen (N), carbon (C), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) input rates according to the nutrient content, rate and frequency of application of EOM, for the different scenarios..

Figure 3 : Difference in soil N supply (ΔN_{supply}), in the first year (year 1) and after 30 years (year 30) between the scenarios with external organic matter application (EOM) and the reference scenario under mineral treatment (without EOM), annual phosphorus (P_{balance}) and potassium (K_{balance}) balance for the scenarios with EOM application.

According to Figure 2, the average K_{balance} across the evaluated EOM scenarios was predominantly negative, with average value of $-26.83 \text{ kg K}_2\text{O ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$. Positive K_{balance} values were only observed with scenarios with application of horse manure, and cattle manure and slurry digestate in Brittany (Figure A5). All negative K_{balance} value suggests that the application of K inputs from EOMs alone may be insufficient to meet the K requirements of crops, potentially leading to K deficiencies and could decrease the crop yield over time if additional K inputs, such as mineral fertilizers, are not applied (Singh V. K. and Dwivedi, 2021).

3.3. Short- and long-term changes in SOC storage and their effects on available water capacity, soil density, and microbial biomass following EOM types

Applying different EOMs in the field leads to variations in the amount of carbon (C) added to the soil, which is critical in enriching agricultural soils by significantly increasing SOC levels. In this study, C inputs from EOM to the soil ranged from 110 to 1237 $\text{kg C ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ (Figure 2). The highest average annual C input rates, exceeding $750 \text{ kg C ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$, were observed in the Versailles Plain scenarios with the application of green waste compost and horse manure, in the Alsace and Brittany scenarios with cattle manure, and Wallonia-Belgium scenario with a combination of cattle manure and other EOMs (cattle manure compost, sugar scum, or cattle slurry) (Figure A1). In contrast, biowaste digestate, limed urban sludge in the Versailles Plain, and energy crop digestate in Lauragais scenarios contributed less than $300 \text{ kg C ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ in C inputs. These results suggest a marked differentiation in C input levels depending on the EOM scenario and highlight regional disparities, with some regions receiving significantly more C inputs compared to others. As illustrated in Figure 4, the SOC storage simulation results demonstrate a substantial initial contribution to C storage under EOM application, showing an average change in $\Delta C_{\text{storage}}$ of $392 \text{ kg C ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$, compared to mineral treatments during the first year of application. However, after 30 years of EOM application, a marked decline in $\Delta C_{\text{storage}}$ was observed, with mean values decreasing to $68 \text{ kg C ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ (Figure 4). While an amount of C was stored initially, the long-term effectiveness of C storage decreased, suggesting that the soil reached a new equilibrium with regard to the considered C input, leading to minimal long-term carbon gains (Moinet et al., 2023). Furthermore, the results also showed considerable variation in SOC storage depending on the type of EOM applied. Specifically, the application of cattle manure, either alone or in combination with other EOMs, as well as green waste compost and cattle manure slurry digestate, resulted in significantly higher $\Delta C_{\text{storage}}$ values, exceeding $400 \text{ kg C ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ (Figure 4), with a peak of $792 \text{ kg C ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ observed in the first year of application (Figure 2). This initial high storage contribution regressed over the long term, with values between 70 and $176 \text{ kg C ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ after 30 years of continuous application of these EOM in cropping systems (Figure 4). For other types of EOMs, contributions to SOC storage followed a similar trend, though with slightly lower initial $\Delta C_{\text{storage}}$ values. In scenario involving limed urban sludge, biowaste digestate, pig slurry, pig slurry digestate, or energy crop digestate, the EOM application also contributed to SOC, with slightly lower initial $\Delta C_{\text{storage}}$ values varied from 34 to $245 \text{ kg C ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ in the first year, subsequently declining to values between 2 and $25 \text{ kg C ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ by the 30th year (Figure 4). These findings suggest that the stabilization of C storage is primarily related to EOM characteristics and application rates

(Levavasseur et al., 2020; Yadav et al., 2024). Consequently, changes in water storage capacity (Δa_{wc}), soil density (Δd_{soil}), and microbial biomass ($\Delta m_{microbial\ biomass}$) relative to mineral treatment appeared to vary systematically according to SOC storage levels (Figure 4). The most pronounced changes after 30 years of application were observed in scenarios with cattle manure, with or without combinations of other EOM types, cattle manure and slurry digestate, green waste compost, and green waste and sludge compost compared to limed urban sludge, biowaste digestate, cattle slurry, energy crop digestate, pig slurry, and pig slurry digestate; with Δa_{wc} ranging from 1 to 4.48 mm, Δd_{soil} from -0.05 to -0.02, and $\Delta m_{microbial\ biomass}$ from 2 500 to 9 515 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ soil. The simulated increase in a_{wc} and the simulated decrease in d_{soil} remained however limited (Figure 4).

3.4. Variations N losses: nitrate leaching, nitrous oxide emissions, and ammonia volatilization following application of different EOM types

The tools simulated the N losses that occur following EOM application, including nitrate (NO_3) leaching, nitrous oxide (N_2O) emissions, and ammonia (NH_3) volatilization, all of which may evolve after the automatic adjustment of mineral N fertilization based on crop needs and simulated N supply. According to Figure 5, the simulation results demonstrated a significant impact of the simulation period on the variation of nitrate leaching ($\Delta \text{NO}_{3\text{leached}}$), nitrous oxide emissions ($\Delta \text{N}_2\text{O}_{\text{emission}}$), and ammonia volatilization ($\Delta \text{NH}_{3\text{volatilized}}$). This indicates that N losses are strongly affected by the repeated application of EOM over time.

In the first year of EOM application, the average $\Delta \text{NO}_{3\text{leached}}$ was 1.23 $\text{kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$, increasing substantially to 4.48 $\text{kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ after 30 years of continuous EOM application (Figure 5). These simulations highlight the long-term effect of applying EOMs, which increases SOM storage. The resulting N mineralization from the higher SOM likely drives the observed increase in NO_3 leaching over time, even if mineral N fertilization was adjusted. Therefore, continuous EOM application appears to boost N availability in the soil, potentially leading to higher N losses, especially through NO_3 leaching. Although some reductions were observed, with negative $\Delta \text{NO}_{3\text{leached}}$ values, in scenarios with cattle manure and slurry digestate in Brittany; cattle manure in Alsace; and green waste compost and cattle manure in Gers (Figure A 6). However, scenario with biowaste digestate in the plains of Versailles, pig slurry digestate, cattle slurry digestate, and pig slurry in Brittany, as well as pig slurry in Alsace, showed a high value of $\Delta \text{NO}_{3\text{leached}}$, ranging from 3.2 to 12.17 $\text{kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ (Figure A 6), compared to compost and manure, in the first year of application. These results highlight a potential drawback of EOMs, which supply high N in soil (Figure 3), as they release large amounts of mineral-N, which are readily available to plants but may be prone to leaching if not fully straight away absorbed by the crop, compared to organic amendments that provide a more gradual release of organic-N (Eriksen et al., 2004). By year 30, the increase in $\Delta \text{NO}_{3\text{leached}}$ was considerable, reaching from 5.76 to 30.75 $\text{kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$, in scenarios with the application of horse manure, green waste compost, and biowaste digestate in the plains of Versailles; cattle manure, pig slurry, pig slurry digestate, and cattle slurry digestate in Brittany; and pig slurry, cattle manure, and green waste and sludge compost in Alsace, where was observed the highest $\Delta \text{NO}_{3\text{leached}}$ exceeded 20 $\text{kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ (Figure A 6).

Figure 4 : Variation in soil carbon storage ($\Delta C_{\text{storage}}$), in the topsoil horizon, in the first year (year 1) and after 30 years (year 30) of external organic matter application (EOM) compared to soil carbon storage in mineral treatment (without EOM); and variation in available water capacity (Δa_{wc}), soil density (Δd_{soil}), and microbial biomass ($\Delta m_{\text{microbial biomass}}$) after 30 years of EOM application compared to the mineral treatment (without EOM)

Figure 5 : Difference in nitrate lixiviation (ΔNO_3 leached), nitrous oxide emissions ($\Delta \text{N}_2\text{O}$ emission), and ammonia volatilization (ΔNH_3 volatilized), in the first year (year 1) and after 30 years (year 30) between the scenarios with external organic matter application (EOM) and the reference scenarios without EOM

In parallel, an increase in N₂O emissions ($\Delta\text{N}_2\text{O}_{\text{emission}}$) was also observed, with the average for all EOMs rising from 0.158 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ in the first year to 0.286 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ after 30 years of EOM applications. These N₂O emissions were notably higher in scenarios with the application of biowaste digestate in the plains of Versailles, pig slurry in Alsace, and energy crop digestate in Lauragais, with $\Delta\text{N}_2\text{O}_{\text{emission}}$ exceeding 0.4 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ in both timeframes (Figure A7). This can be associated with the timing of application during the late winter (Table A1) (Li et al., 2024; Winkhart et al., 2024). The scenario with the application of cattle manure, cattle slurry, and cattle manure compost also showed a significant level of $\Delta\text{N}_2\text{O}_{\text{emission}}$ ($\Delta\text{N}_2\text{O}_{\text{emission}} > 0.29$ kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹), in the first year of application.

After 30 years of application, $\Delta\text{N}_2\text{O}_{\text{emission}}$ potentially increased in scenarios using horse manure, green waste compost, cattle manure, cattle slurry, cattle manure compost, and certain cattle manure and slurry digestates, as well as pig slurry digestate (Figure A5). These emissions were higher both in comparison to mineral fertilizer alone and relative to $\Delta\text{N}_2\text{O}_{\text{emission}}$ observed in the first year (Figure A7). These increases in N₂O emissions over time could be attributed to: (1) the characteristics of these organic amendments, which contribute significantly to soil SOM levels and likely promote increased soil N mineralization (Kelley et al., 2024); (2) the crop management systems, particularly if the soil is not adequately covered during periods of higher N availability induced by mineralization. The excess mineralized N, if not absorbed by the crop, can increase NO₃ leaching and denitrification losses, ultimately leading to higher N₂O emissions (Saha et al., 2021). These findings suggest that effective management of EOM application, particularly in terms of timing and type, is crucial to minimize N losses and mitigate their environmental impact. The studies reviewed provide insights into the factors influencing these emissions and potential mitigation strategies. In contrast, $\Delta\text{N}_2\text{O}_{\text{emission}}$ exhibited a potential reduction after 30 years in scenarios with cattle manure, cattle slurry, pig slurry, pig slurry digestate, and cattle manure and slurry digestates. This decrease was observed relative to the 30th-year mineral treatment and compared to the initial year's $\Delta\text{N}_2\text{O}_{\text{emission}}$ (Figure 5). Following the adjustment of mineral N fertilization based on crop needs, over time, EOM applications reduced the reliance on mineral N fertilizers, which are typically associated with increased N₂O emissions in the field.

In contrast, nitrogen losses through ammonia volatilization ($\text{NH}_3_{\text{volatilized}}$) exhibited an overall decline, with $\Delta\text{NH}_3_{\text{volatilized}}$ decreasing from an initial average of 3.08 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ in the first year to 1.48 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ by the 30th year of continuous EOM application (Figure 5). This result suggests that long-term EOM applications can enhance soil N supply while decreasing reliance on mineral N fertilizers, which may have contributed to the observed reduction in NH₃ volatilization compared to mineral-only treatments over time. The type of EOM applied also strongly influenced NH₃ volatilization rates. For instance, the application of certain EOM types—including green waste compost, limed urban sludge, green waste and sludge compost, biowaste digestate, and cattle manure compost—demonstrated a potential to reduce NH₃ volatilization relative to mineral treatments, even in the first year, with negative $\Delta\text{NH}_3_{\text{volatilized}}$ values. Over the 30 years, this reduction became more pronounced, particularly with amendments such as cattle manure, horse manure, biowaste digestate, and energy crop digestate, each showing $\Delta\text{NH}_3_{\text{volatilized}}$ values of -10 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ or lower (Figure A5). This confirms a reduced need for mineral N fertilization, which in turn further limits ammonia

volatilization. However, the scenarios with cattle slurry, cattle manure and slurry digestate, pig slurry, and pig slurry digestate application were associated with the highest $\Delta\text{NH}_{3\text{volatilized}}$ values due to their high ammonium nitrogen ($\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$) content, which is highly susceptible to volatilization. $\Delta\text{NH}_{3\text{volatilized}}$ of these EOM scenarios ranged from 5 to 13 $\text{kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ in the first year, and 3 to 12 $\text{kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ after 30 years of application (Figure 5). Nonetheless, N volatilization losses are strongly affected by factors such as application timing and immediate incorporation into the soil, both of which can either exacerbate or mitigate ammonia volatilization (Dannenmann et al., 2024; Hwang et al., 2022; Pedersen and Hafner, 2023).

3.5. EOM effect on soil trace element content

The application of EOMs introduces varying levels of trace element (TE) into the soil, influenced by the type, dosage, and frequency of EOM application. While the PROLEG tool does not simulate the availability of these metals, it can evaluate their accumulation—specifically for Zn, Cu, Pb, Ni, Hg, Cr, and Cd—as shown in Figure 6. Overall, applications of green waste compost, limed urban sludge, cattle manure with cattle manure compost, cattle manure and slurry digestate contributed the highest content of TE to the soil, with each of these EOM types increasing the concentration of at least three TE compared to other EOM applications (Figure 6).

In more detail, zinc levels showed the highest increase among TE following EOM application, with notable accumulation in scenarios with green waste compost, cattle manure, and combinations involving cattle manure with either cattle slurry, cattle manure compost, or sugar scum, where $\Delta\text{Zn}_{\text{soil}}$ exceeded $0.12 \text{ mg kg}^{-1} \text{ soil year}^{-1}$. Copper concentrations also rose significantly, particularly with applications of limed urban sludge, green waste compost, pig slurry, pig slurry digestate, and green waste and sludge compost, as well as cattle manure combined with cattle manure compost, with $\Delta\text{Cu}_{\text{soil}}$ increases exceeding $0.04 \text{ mg kg}^{-1} \text{ soil year}^{-1}$. Similarly, lead content in soil increased markedly in scenarios using horse manure, green waste compost, green waste and sludge compost, and cattle manure paired with either sugar scum or cattle manure compost in Belgium, resulting in $\Delta\text{Pb}_{\text{soil}}$ levels above $0.02 \text{ mg kg}^{-1} \text{ soil year}^{-1}$ —substantially higher than other EOMs. For nickel, concentrations increased most prominently under applications of horse manure, green waste compost, limed urban sludge, cattle manure with sugar scum, and cattle manure and slurry digestate, where $\Delta\text{Ni}_{\text{soil}}$ surpassed $0.0023 \text{ mg kg}^{-1} \text{ soil year}^{-1}$. Although mercury levels were generally low, measurable increases occurred with applications of horse manure, green waste compost, limed urban sludge, cattle slurry, cattle manure and slurry digestate, and green waste and sludge compost, with $\Delta\text{Hg}_{\text{soil}}$ reaching up to $4.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mg kg}^{-1} \text{ soil year}^{-1}$. These findings highlight the considerable variability in TE accumulation across different EOM treatments, underscoring the importance of selecting appropriate EOMs to balance agronomic benefits with potential risks of TE buildup in soil.

In contrast to other trace elements, cadmium and chromium levels decreased following the application of EOM. The EOM application enhances the P balance in the field, allowing for a reduction in mineral P fertilizer use. The reduction in mineral P inputs has contributed to decreased levels of Cd and Cr in the soil. The effect was particularly pronounced in scenarios

with cattle manure, cattle manure and slurry digestate, a combination of cattle manure and cattle slurry, pig manure, and pig manure digestates. Under these EOM, the changes in soil Cd ($\Delta\text{Pb}_{\text{soil}}$) and Cr ($\Delta\text{Cr}_{\text{soil}}$) levels ranged from -0.0012 to -0.0005 mg kg^{-1} soil year $^{-1}$ and from -0.014 to -0.005 mg kg^{-1} soil year $^{-1}$, respectively. This suggests that higher P contributions from EOMs reduce the need for mineral P fertilizers, thereby further lowering Cd and Cr contamination in the soil (Mamun et al., 2022; Suciú et al., 2022).

Figure 6 : Differences in cadmium ($\Delta\text{Cd}_{\text{soil}}$), copper ($\Delta\text{Cu}_{\text{soil}}$), nickel ($\Delta\text{Ni}_{\text{soil}}$), lead ($\Delta\text{Pb}_{\text{soil}}$), zinc ($\Delta\text{Zn}_{\text{soil}}$), mercury ($\Delta\text{Hg}_{\text{soil}}$), and chromium ($\Delta\text{Cr}_{\text{soil}}$) soil contents after 30 years between the scenarios with external organic matter (EOM) application and the reference scenarios (without EOM).

However, an exception was observed for Cr with the application of green waste compost and green waste and sludge compost, which led to an increase in soil Cr concentrations, with $\Delta C_{\text{Cr soil}}$ reaching up to $0.32 \text{ mg kg}^{-1} \text{ soil year}^{-1}$. This increase can be attributed to the low P content of these composts, necessitating higher mineral P application rates to meet crop P needs and thereby introducing additional Cr into the soil. Furthermore, these composts contain inherently higher levels of Cr, significantly contributing to Cr accumulation in the soil. These findings highlight the dual role of EOMs in nutrient management and contamination risk. While EOMs can reduce reliance on mineral fertilizers and lower Cd and Cr contamination, specific compost types, such as green waste and sludge, may require careful management to prevent excess Cr accumulation.

3.6. Greenhouse gas emissions from different types of EOM: comprehensive comparison with and without storage and treatment

The application of EOM to soil is widely recognized as an effective practice for mitigating GHG emissions through C sequestration. Overall, as illustrated in Figure 7, substantial reductions in GHG emissions were observed during the first year of EOM application compared to mineral treatments, without taking into account the GHG emissions from EOM storage and treatment. However, after 30 years of continuous EOM application, the effectiveness of EOM in reducing emissions decreased significantly compared to mineral treatments. When accounting for emissions from storage and treatment, some fields treated with EOM showed an overall increase in emissions with positive $\Delta \text{GHG}_{\text{emission}}$, highlighting potential trade-offs in sustained EOM application.

In the first year of application, the average $\Delta \text{GHG}_{\text{emission}}$ value was $-1549.45 \text{ kg CO}_2 \text{ eq ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$, but over time, it increased to $-394 \text{ kg CO}_2 \text{ eq ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$, after 30 years of continuous EOM application without considering the GHG emission from the storage and the treatment (Figure 7). As illustrated in Figure A9, this reduction in the GHG emission balance was primarily driven by the initial increase in SOC storage, and a decrease in GHG emissions associated with NPK fertilizer production for some scenarios (e.g. with application of digestate). However, as SOC stabilized and $\Delta C_{\text{storage}}$ also declined over time, this logically led to a lower GHG emission balance with repeated EOM applications and increased $\Delta \text{GHG}_{\text{emission}}$ compared to the first year of application. Additionally, over time, a slight decrease in GHG emissions associated with NPK fertilizer production was observed (Figure A10), following the saving fertilizers in both N or P according to the type of EOM applied. However, a slight increase in N_2O also contributed to an increase of $\Delta \text{GHG}_{\text{emission}}$ (Figure A10).

In more detail, GHG emission reductions were notably higher in scenarios with cattle manure, cattle manure and slurry digestate, and cattle manure with cattle slurry, with $\Delta \text{GHG}_{\text{emission}}$ values below $-2300 \text{ kg CO}_2 \text{ eq ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ (excluding storage and treatment emissions) in Brittany (Figure A9), related to the high $\Delta C_{\text{storage}}$ observed in the first year of application. A reduction in $\Delta \text{GHG}_{\text{emission}}$ values, up to $-1300 \text{ kg CO}_2 \text{ eq ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ compared to mineral treatments, was also observed with applications of green waste compost and horse manure in the Versailles plain scenarios, cattle manure and green waste and sludge compost in Alsace, and cattle manure with cattle manure compost or sugar scum in Wallonia, Belgium (Figure A9). These results suggest that EOM applications, which significantly contribute to SOC storage in the soil, lead to

substantial GHG emission reductions, particularly in the initial years of application. Conversely, lower reductions were noted in scenarios with limed urban sludge, biowaste digestate, energy crop digestate, cattle slurry, or pig slurry alone, in the first year of EOM application. Over a 30-year application period, the impact of EOM on $\Delta\text{GHG}_{\text{emission}}$ decreased for all scenarios, with reductions ranging from -1051 to 253 kg CO₂ eq ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ depending on the type of EOM (Figure 7). The application of cattle manure, cattle manure and slurry digestate, and cattle manure applied with cattle slurry consistently resulted in greater reductions in GHG emissions compared to other EOM treatments in the long-term effect, regardless of the GHGs emitted during EOM storage and processing (Figure 7).

However, when accounting for GHG emissions from storage and processing, a similar trend was observed in the initial year, with reductions noted in GHG emissions tied to storage and processing phases. The average $\Delta\text{GHG}_{\text{emissions}}$ value due to storage and treatment were quantified at -459.6 kg CO₂ eq ha⁻¹ year⁻¹. Contrastingly, after 30 years of EOM application, $\Delta\text{GHG}_{\text{emission}}$ increased to 695.9 kg CO₂-eq ha⁻¹ year⁻¹, indicating an accrual of emissions over time. Notably, the highest $\Delta\text{GHG}_{\text{emissions}}$ following 30 years were observed with applications of green waste compost in the Plaine de Versailles, Gers, and Lauragais regions; cattle manure and its compost variant in Wallonia, Belgium; as well as limed sludge, biowaste digestate in the Plaine de Versailles, and energy crop digestate in Lauragais. These applications showed $\Delta\text{GHG}_{\text{emission}}$ values between 990 and 4341 CO₂ eq ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ (Figure A10). These results highlight the short-term GHG mitigation potential of EOM applications, although long-term sustainability depends on storage and treatment practices as well as the specific type of EOM used. This data suggests that emissions from storage and treatment may progressively offset the GHG mitigation potential of EOM applications. These insights prompt a broader question on the allocation of process emissions to agricultural sectors, particularly when processing urban waste. Indeed, in the emissions inventory used in PROLEG (Yadav et al., 2024); whereas most of the emissions related to manure were not allocated to manure but rather to breeding activities, emissions during composting of urban waste were allocated to the compost. Additionally, it raises the consideration of whether alternative uses for these EOMs could yield a different GHG emissions profile.

Figure 7 : Differences in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions under EOM application and mineral fertilizers (without EOM application), in the first year of EOM application (Year 1) and after 30 years of EOM application, with and without the GHG emission from the treatment and storage.

3.7. Limitations and practical guidelines

3.7.1. Limitations of tool

This study faced several limitations that impacted the applicability and accuracy of simulations for certain European cropping systems. Specifically, some scenarios could not be effectively simulated, primarily due to factors related to soil types, crop associations, data quality, and the representativeness of simulated farming practices.

- a- *Soil type constraints*: In the Netherlands, for example, peatland soils with high carbon content were outside the simulation range of the tool, limiting its capacity to simulate these soil types accurately. Peatland's high organic carbon levels exceeded the tool's functional range, preventing a realistic simulation of nutrient dynamics in such environments.
- b- *Crop associations*: The tool was configured primarily to simulate monocultures rather than complex crop associations within a growing season. As a result, simplified crop representations were used, which likely reduced the ecological realism of certain cropping systems and limited the applicability of the simulations for diversified agricultural landscapes.
- c- *Incomplete and imprecise data*: Some scenarios included data that were either incomplete or insufficiently detailed to meet the tool's simulation requirements. In particular, specific information on irrigation practices or management inputs was sometimes lacking, which compromised simulation accuracy by introducing assumptions that may not fully align with actual farming conditions.
- d- *Poor simulation of crop growth and N uptake*: The study relied on generalized cropping systems commonly used in research rather than those practiced by farmers, leading to discrepancies in simulation outcomes. This mismatch often produced unrealistic results, particularly regarding yield estimates and nutrient flow simulations. For instance, simulated N flows did not always align with expected real-world behavior, potentially misrepresenting nutrient dynamics and limiting the validity of these projections for practical agricultural decision-making.

Although the simulation tool successfully handled a wide variety of large-scale arable cropping systems, its scope remains limited. Currently, the tool is best suited to simulate annual arable crops on a large scale and lacks the flexibility to represent more diverse cropping systems such as perennial crops and permanent grasslands. Consequently, while this study offers insights into large-scale European arable cropping systems, it does not yet capture the full range of agricultural diversity across Europe. These limitations highlight the need for future work to expand the tool's capabilities, especially to accommodate a wider diversity of European soils, cropping systems, and data inputs.

3.7.2. Representativeness of the simulated case studies

This study incorporates expert insights on farming practices in France and Belgium, but its geographic focus limits the diversity of conditions simulated, excluding significant regional differences in practices, climate, and resource availability. Although countries such as the Netherlands, Lithuania, Turkey, Italy, Spain, and Austria were initially considered, practical constraints narrowed the scope to France and Belgium, which may not fully capture the variability across Europe. Furthermore, within each case study, variations in application rates, timing, and amendment types were not fully explored, limiting the range of agricultural scenarios modeled. Expanding these variables would enhance the representativeness of the study by better reflecting the diversity of real-world practices. Additionally, future developments like increased availability of new amendments (e.g., digestates, biochar) were not included. Factoring in these evolving elements would strengthen the model's robustness and applicability, providing more comprehensive insights into real-world agricultural conditions. Finally, future studies should consider the impacts of climate change on EOM performance. Although this study did not address climate factors directly, anticipated changes in temperature, precipitation, and seasonality are likely to affect soil needs, nutrient cycles, and amendment efficacy. Incorporating climate projections into future models would improve predictions of EOM effectiveness under changing environmental conditions.

3.7.3. Practical guidelines

The potential of EOM to improve soil health in European cropping systems is promising, positioning EOM as a sustainable complement to mineral fertilizers. Applying EOM can enhance soil C storage, improve certain soil properties, and reduce N fertilizer needs in both the short and long term, depending on the EOM type. Some EOM types can also decrease N volatilization over time when used as soil amendments. However, to fully realize these benefits while minimizing risks, several practical guidelines emerge from this study.

A primary concern with long-term EOM use is the risk of NO_3 leaching and increased N_2O emissions, even with adjustments to mineral N fertilization based on soil N supply following EOM application. Addressing these issues requires optimizing EOM management practices, including refining the timing and methods of application, increasing soil coverage during high-risk periods, and adjusting crop rotations to minimize nutrient losses. However, these optimizations should be tested in the field and/or with the PROLEG tool to ensure their adaptability and effectiveness.

Certain EOMs, such as digestates, are linked to increased N volatilization and should be managed with practices such as soil incorporation, application timing adjustments, and acidification when needed. Additionally, TE accumulation presents a potential risk; limiting contamination at the source is essential to prevent soil degradation.

It is also essential to take a balanced approach to GHG emissions from EOM use. A fair assessment of EOM's net emissions profile, weighed against its benefits for sustainable farming, will help support its acceptance as a viable long-term solution. It is important to recognize that EOMs alone cannot fully replace mineral fertilizers or substantially improve all

soil properties; combining EOM with other agroecological practices will be essential for developing truly sustainable farming systems.

4. CONCLUSION

This study confirms the multiple positive effects of EOM products on soil quality, particularly when integrated into practices currently implemented by farmers. However, the magnitude of these effects varies significantly depending on the EOM type, rate, and frequency of application. The benefits observed include enhanced C storage, improved N supply, and better P and K balance, leading to mineral fertilizer savings, alongside challenges related to N losses, soil contamination, and GHG emissions. To ensure the sustainable use of EOM in agriculture, it is crucial to focus on mitigating the long-term negative impacts associated with repeated EOM applications. Efforts should be made to reduce unnecessary nutrient surpluses and optimize nutrient cycling while prioritizing strategies aimed at minimizing GHG emissions, particularly during the treatment and storage phases. These measures are essential to mitigate the overall environmental footprint of EOM applications and support the broader goal of reducing agriculture's contribution to climate change. Given the diverse impacts of EOM on soil health, it is important to tailor management strategies to local conditions and continue refining EOM practices. Future research should further explore the long-term effects of EOM use, particularly concerning GHG emissions, and seek to develop practical solutions that maximize its benefits while minimizing its risks. By addressing these challenges, EOM has the potential to significantly contribute to the sustainability of European agriculture, offering a viable alternative to traditional mineral fertilizers and supporting soil health across diverse farming systems. EOM use should however be combined with other sustainable practices to develop agroecological cropping systems.

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Table A 1 : Overview of external organic matter (EOM) applications in cropping systems: position in rotation, fresh matter doses per hectare, and application periods across regions of France, Wallonia-Belgium, Turkey, Lithuania, and the Netherlands

Cropping systems: doses, application period and stage						
France						
<i>Versailles plain - A</i>		Rapeseed	Winter wheat	Mustard ^(b)	Grain maize	Winter wheat
Biowaste digestate		14 t ha⁻¹				Winter barley
		Before the sowing				20 t ha⁻¹
		Late summer				At the early stem elongation stage
Green waste compost				30 t ha⁻¹		Early spring
				At the early vegetative stage		
				Late summer		
Horse manure				20 t ha⁻¹		
				At the early vegetative stage		
				Late summer		
Limed urban sludge		10 t ha⁻¹				
		Before the sowing				
		Late summer				
<i>Versailles plain - B</i>		Rapeseed	Winter wheat	Winter wheat		Winter barley
Biowaste digestate		14 t ha⁻¹		20 t ha⁻¹		
		Before the sowing		At the early stem elongation stage		
		Late summer		Late summer		
Green waste compost			30 t ha⁻¹			
			Before the sowing			
			Late summer			
Horse manure			20 t ha ⁻¹			
			Before the sowing			
			Late summer			
Limed urban sludge		10 t ha⁻¹				
		Before the sowing				
		Late summer				

^(a) Group refers to the scenario group within each region based on variations in cropping systems and soil types used in the simulation.

^(b) Nitrogen catch crop

^(c) Energy cover crop

Cropping systems : Doses, application period and stage

France			
Brittany - C & D	Winter wheat	Mustard ^(b)	Silage maize
Cattle manure			30 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Early spring
Cattle manure & cattle slurry			<i>Cattle manure</i> 20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Early spring <i>Cattle slurry</i> 18 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Spring
Cattle manure & slurry digestate	30 t ha⁻¹ At the early stem elongation stage Early spring		30 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Spring
Cattle slurry			45 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Spring
Pig slurry	27 t ha⁻¹ At the early stem elongation stage Early spring		27 t ha⁻¹ At the sowing Spring
Pig slurry digestate	30 t ha⁻¹ At the early stem elongation stage Early spring		30 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Spring
Brittany - E & F	Winter wheat	Rye or barley ^(c)	Silage maize
Cattle manure		30 t ha⁻¹ At the early stem elongation stage Early spring	
Cattle manure & slurry digestate	30 t ha⁻¹ At the early stem elongation stage Late winter		30 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Spring
Cattle slurry			45 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Early spring

Table A 1 (continued) : Overview of EOM applications in cropping systems: position in rotation, fresh doses per hectare, and application periods across regions of France, Wallonia-Belgium, Turkey, Lithuania, and the Netherlands

Cropping systems : Doses, application period and stage						
France						
<i>Alsace - G & H</i>	Grain maize	Grain maize	Grain maize	Winter wheat	Mustard ^(b)	Soyabean
Cattle manure		22 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Early autumn		23 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Summer		
Green waste & sludge compost		10 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Early autumn		10 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Summer		
Pig slurry	31.5 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Late winter	31.5 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Late winter	31.5 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Late winter			
<i>Gers- I</i>	Grain maize	Grain maize	Grain maize			
Cattle manure	20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Late winter	20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Late winter	20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Late winter			
Green waste compost	9 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Late winter					
<i>Lauragais- J</i>	Durum wheat	Sunflower				
Green waste compost		30 t ha⁻¹ Before the winter Early autumn				
<i>Lauragais- K</i>	Durum wheat	Sunflower	Rye or barley ^(c)			
Energy crop digestate-1	25 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Early autumn					
Energy crop digestate-2	25 t ha⁻¹ At the early stem elongation stage Early spring					

^(a) Group refers to the scenario group within each region based on variations in cropping systems and soil types used in the simulation.

^(b) Nitrogen catch crop

^(c) Energy cover crop

Table A 1 (continued) : Overview of EOM applications in cropping systems: position in rotation, fresh doses per hectare, and application periods across regions of France, Wallonia-Belgium, Turkey, Lithuania, and the Netherlands

Cropping systems : Doses, application period and stage									
Belgium									
<i>Wallonia Bruelette- L</i>									
Cattle slurry & Cattle manure	Mixture of legumes ^(b)	Sugar beet	Winter wheat	Mixture of legumes ^(b)	Consumption potatoes	Winter wheat			
	<i>Cattle manure</i> 20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Summer	<i>Cattle slurry</i> 15 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Early spring		<i>Cattle manure</i> 15 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Summer					
<i>Wallonia Awans- M</i>									
Cattle manure & Cattle manure compost	Winter wheat	Rapeseed	Crucifers ^(b)	Consumption potatoes	Winter wheat	Mixture of legumes ^(b)	Peas for canning	Mixture of legumes ^(b)	Sugar beet
		<i>Cattle manure compost</i> 25 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Summer						<i>Cattle manure</i> 25 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Late summer	
<i>Wallonia Huy (Solières) - N</i>									
Cattle manure & Sugar scum	Mixture of legumes ^(b)	Sugar beet	Winter wheat	Rapeseed	Mixture of legumes ^(b)	Silage maize	Winter wheat		
	<i>Cattle manure</i> 20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Summer				<i>Cattle manure</i> 20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Summer <i>Sugar scum</i> 10 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Summer				

^(a) Group refers to the scenario group within each region based on variations in cropping systems and soil types used in the simulation.

^(b) Nitrogen catch crop

^(c) Energy cover crop

Cropping systems : Doses, application period and stage					
Turkey					
<i>Adana – O & P</i>					
Certified Turkey	compost	Winter wheat	Grain maize		
		5 t ha⁻¹	5 t ha⁻¹		
		Before the sowing	Before the sowing		
		Early autumn	Autumn		
	Winter wheat	Sunflower			
	5 t ha⁻¹				
	Before the sowing				
	Early autumn				
	Winter wheat	Grain maize			
Cattle manure		20 t ha⁻¹	20 t ha⁻¹		
		Before the sowing	Before the sowing		
		Autumn	Late spring		
		Winter wheat	Sunflower		
	20 t ha⁻¹				
	Before the sowing				
	Early autumn				
Lithuania					
<i>Anykščiai - Eastern</i>					
Green compost	waste	Winter wheat	Spring barley	Cosumption potatoes	Spring rapeseed
		23.7 t ha⁻¹	23.7 t ha⁻¹	23.7 t ha⁻¹	23.7 t ha⁻¹
		Before the sowing	Before the sowing	Before the sowing	Before the sowing
		Early spring	Early spring	Early spring	Spring
Green waste and sludge compost		15.5 t ha⁻¹	15.5 t ha⁻¹	15.5 t ha⁻¹	15.5 t ha⁻¹
		Before the sowing	Before the sowing	Before the sowing	Before the sowing
		Early spring	Early spring	Early spring	Spring
Cattle compost	manure	44.5 t ha⁻¹	44.5 t ha⁻¹	44.5 t ha⁻¹	44.5 t ha⁻¹
		Before the sowing	Before the sowing	Before the sowing	Before the sowing
		Early spring	Early spring	Early spring	Early spring
Poultry manure		16.5 t ha⁻¹	16.5 t ha⁻¹	16.5 t ha⁻¹	16.5 t ha⁻¹
		Before the sowing	Before the sowing	Before the sowing	Before the sowing
		Early spring	Early spring	Early spring	Early spring

^(a) Group refers to the scenario group within each region based on variations in cropping systems and soil types used in the simulation.

^(b) Nitrogen catch crop

^(c) Energy cover crop

Table A 1 (continued) : Overview of EOM applications in cropping systems: position in rotation, fresh doses per hectare, and application periods across regions of France, Wallonia-Belgium, Turkey, Lithuania, and the Netherlands

Cropping systems : Doses, application period and stage					
Netherlands					
<i>Drenthe</i>	Starch potatoes	Spring barley	Grass cover crop ^(b)	Starch potatoes	Sugar beet
Pig slurry	20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Early spring			20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Early spring	20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Early spring
Green waste compost & pig slurry	<i>Green waste compost</i> 20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Early spring <i>Pig slurry</i> 20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Spring			<i>Green waste compost</i> 20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Early spring <i>Pig slurry</i> 20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Spring	<i>Green waste compost</i> 20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Early spring <i>Pig slurry</i> 20 t ha⁻¹ Before the sowing Spring

^(a) Group refers to the scenario group within each region based on variations in cropping systems and soil types used in the simulation.

^(b) Nitrogen catch crop

^(c) Energy cover crop

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Figure A 5 : Annual potassium (K) balance all fields receiving mineral fertilizer (without EOM) and under EOM application. Letters A to N represent scenario groups within each region based on variations in cropping systems and soil types used in the simulation, as indicated in Table 2

Figure A 6 : Increase in nitrate (N₃O) leaching, at the initial situation and after 30 years of EOM application compared to the leached N in the mineral treatment (without EOM) in each simulated scenario group. Letters A to N represent the scenario groups within each region based on variations in cropping systems and soil types used in the simulation, as indicated in Table 2

Figure A 7 : Increase in nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions, at the initial situation and after 30 years of EOM application compared to the leached N in the mineral treatment (without EOM) in each simulated scenario group. Letters A to N represent the scenario groups within each region based on variations in cropping systems and soil types used in the simulation, as indicated in Table 2.

Figure A 8 : Increase in ammonia (NH₃) volatilization, at the initial situation and after 30 years of EOM application compared to the leached N in the mineral treatment (without EOM) in each simulated scenario group. Letters A to N represent the scenario groups within each region based on variations in cropping systems and soil types used in the simulation, as indicated in Table 2.

Figure A 9 : Differences in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions under EOM application and mineral fertilizers (without EOM application), in the first year of EOM application (Year 1), without the GHG emission from the treatment and storage. The stacked bars indicate the different sources of GHG in the cropping system. The red point in each bar represents the total values of GHG emissions for each treatment. Letters A to N represent the scenario groups within each region based on variations in cropping systems and soil types used in the simulation, as indicated in Table 2

Figure A 10 : Differences in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions under EOM application and mineral fertilizers (without EOM application), after 30 years of EOM application (Year 30), without the GHG emission from the treatment and storage. The stacked bars indicate the different sources of GHG in the cropping system. The red point in each bar represents the total values of GHG emissions for each treatment. Letters A to N represent the scenario groups within each region based on variations in cropping systems and soil types used in the simulation, as indicated in Table 2.

Figure A 11 : Differences in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions under EOM application and mineral fertilizers (without EOM application), in the first year of EOM application (Year 1), with the GHG emission from the treatment and storage. The stacked bars indicate the different sources of GHG in the cropping system. The red point in each bar represents the total values of GHG emissions for each treatment. Letters A to N represent the scenario groups within each region based on variations in cropping systems and soil types used in the simulation, as indicated in Table 2.

Figure A 12 : Differences in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions under EOM application and mineral fertilizers (without EOM application), after 30 years of EOM application (Year 30), with the GHG emission from the treatment and storage. The stacked bars indicate the different sources of GHG in the cropping system. The red point in each bar represents the total values of GHG emissions for each treatment. Letters A to N represent the scenario groups within each region based on variations in cropping systems and soil types used in the simulation, as indicated in Table 2.